

Accessing High Quality Mathematics Instruction in Measures: Reporting on a Constructivist and Project-based Approach in Primary Schools

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International and national assessments reveal that Irish primary pupils perform relatively poorly in measurement. This study explores the impact of a constructivist teaching intervention on pupil's understanding and experiences with measures. Two groups of sixth class pupils, control and intervention, from similar class sizes and school settings participated in the study. Pre-intervention assessments evaluated proficiency in Measures. The intervention group participated in a six-week intervention where pupils engaged in constructivist, project-based activities. They also participated in focus group interviews and surveys investigating their experiences and dispositions towards measurement. During the same period, the control group engaged with measures using a traditional textbook teaching approach. Following the intervention, both groups engaged in post-test assessments and a maths trail practical test to assess their hands-on measurement skills. The intervention group again participated in surveys and focus group interviews. Findings reveal that the intervention had little impact on content performance and minimal improvements in problem solving skills. The practical tests highlighted significant improvement for the intervention group in the 'hands on' application of skills such as physically measuring items, conservation, and estimation and more positive attitudes toward mathematics.

Introduction

Certain areas of the Mathematics Curriculum align themselves more readily to real life maths, where connections are made between the abstract world of the subject and everyday contexts. Nowhere is this more evident than the strand of measurement and its cognate areas of Length, Area, Weight, Capacity, Time and Money. Perplexingly, these are the same areas where Irish pupils perform below other content domains in international comparisons such as the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), and are also mirrored in our national studies. In the TIMSS 2015 study Irish pupils outperformed thirty-seven Organisation for Economic Development (OECD) countries. However, performance in geometric shapes and measurement was our lowest in the assessment and described as a 'relative weakness' when scrutinised against our mean score in maths (Clerkin et al., 2016). Similarly, our subscale score for the cognitive domains of 'Reasoning' was significantly lower than our overall maths scale score (compared to 'knowing', which was significantly higher). Similar patterns are evident in international and national assessments (Eivers et al., 2007; Surgenor et al., 2006), which recount Irish pupil's limited ability on items requiring higher order thinking skills particularly in real world contexts, and in the most recent TIMSS 2019 assessment (Perkins & Clerkin, 2019). Our more traditional instructional methodologies and reliance on textbook guidance may, we argue, contribute towards improving operation skills and procedural fluency while overlooking the higher order skills of Applying, Problem Solving, Integrating and Connecting.

Review of the Literature

Constructivism and Mathematics Education

A fundamental tenet of maths curricula in Ireland is child centred learning which places the child's personal experience at the heart of classroom pedagogy as active agents within an environment of discovery. Exploration, as opposed to teacher-led instruction, are seen as the scaffolds upon where incremental learning develops. The Mathematics Primary School Curriculum (NCCA, 1999) states 'a constructivist approach to maths learning involves the child as an active participant in the learning process' and that 'the importance of providing the child with structured opportunities to engage in exploratory activity cannot be over-emphasised' (p.5). Drafted plans for the prospective curriculum are equally congruous to this idea. Situating the child and their exploration at the centre of maths classroom methodologies traces its roots to the theoretical framework of constructivism. Fosnot (2005) aptly describes constructivism as what 'knowing' is and how one comes to 'know'. Indeed, Glasersfeld (1996) emphasises that we do not and cannot 'share' meaning; knowledge is acquired through involvement with content instead of imitation or repetition. Teachers who base their practice on constructivism reject the notion that meaning can be passed on to learners via symbols and transmission; that learners can incorporate exact copies of teacher's understanding for their own use; that whole concepts can be broken into discrete sub-skills and that concepts can be taught out of context. Indeed, constructivist teachers reject such pedagogies of control or telling (Laroche et al., 1998) and embrace constructivist-informed teaching styles that mark a conscious effort to move from traditional, didactic and memory-oriented transmission models (Cannella & Reiff, 1994) to more student-centred approaches.

The Role of Textbooks

It is difficult to envision how mathematical understanding can be deepened and developed without incorporating opportunities for mathematical discussion and a forum where students' collaborative efforts can be communicated and visualised. Textbooks tend to portion learning into bite-sized pieces where little thinking is needed, and mathematical complexity is minimised. Memorising facts and formulas, Delaney (2016) contends, is often valued over presenting tasks that require thoughtful and creative responses. Problems are instead presented to pupils in a predefined way, an approach Noddings (1985) argues that removes the opportunity to wrestle with the problematic situation. Consequently, Delaney (2012) argues that traditional reliance on textbooks in Ireland is not conducive to developing children's problem-solving abilities, since, as he highlights, many of the problems in Irish maths textbooks are of poor quality. Indeed, the 2014 National Assessments of English Reading and Mathematics reports that instructional textbooks and teacher-led maths instruction acted as the main method of current classroom practice and report that 'a lower allocation of time to teaching the mathematical processes of reasoning and applying ... compared with the more basic process of Knowing' (Shiel et al., 2014, p.4). Similarly, evaluation of the implementation of the revised curriculum in maths (DES, 2005a) found that in a significant number of classrooms, there was an overemphasis on didactic methodologies,

teacher talk and the use of a single textbook. These findings were supported by Surgenor et al. (2006) who report that 83% of time in maths classes was allocated to instruction, with 95.5% of pupils reporting that the class textbook was afforded daily usage. Conversely, only 8.7% of over 4,000 pupils surveyed experienced daily contact with concrete materials. That said, more recent studies provide welcome evidence of a decrease in the reliance on textbooks and increase in the use of manipulatives in teaching of mathematics at primary level (O’Meara et al., 2019; Johnson et al., 2020).

Methodology

This action research study (see Figure 1) was a pre-test, post-test control-group design. Two intact classes were selected as research participants. Both were from similar rural co-educational schools with comparable ability and class sizes. The intervention group consisted of 30 pupils (8 boys, 22 girls) and the control group had 31 pupils (16 boys, 15 girls). Ethical approval was gained from the college ethics committee; pupil’ assent, parental and school consent were also received. This paper reports on the research question:

In what ways do constructivist and project based approaches to teaching support children’s understandings of and experiences with measurement?

Figure 1

Action Research Design

The Intervention

Both classes covered three Measures strand units (length, area, weight), allocating two weeks of teaching to each. The intervention group, taught by one of the researchers, engaged in a constructivist informed teaching and learning intervention focusing on collaborative project-based learning, hands-on activities and opportunities to share strategies and engage in mathematical discourse. The class textbook was not used as a resource during the intervention. The control group enacted no changes to their regular classroom practice. They experienced a traditional classroom teaching approach where the textbook was the primary instructional guide.

Data Collection

This mixed methods approach collected both qualitative and quantitative data (table 1). Prior to the intervention, both groups were administered (1) the Drumcondra Primary Mathematics Test and (2) a measures content test to determine their mathematical competency in measures. A survey (modified from Fennema & Sherman (1978) *Mathematics Attitude Scales* and focus group interviews were also carried out at this stage with the intervention group to ascertain their experiences of and attitudes towards maths. Following the 6-week instructional period, both groups engaged in a maths trail to assess their kinaesthetic skills of measurement and repeated assessments (1) and (2) above. The intervention group engaged again with the survey and focus groups to investigate how they perceived and experienced the intervention. Participant observation and the use of a reflective diary were also employed. Observations gave rich insights into the challenges presented by both content and social dynamics for maths discussions and collaborative tasks. A reflective diary documented ongoing observations as pupils participated in each of the cycles of intervention. These substantially aided planning for subsequent lesson design and acted as a source of data and aide memoir when findings from the study were collated.

Data Analysis

Following the completion of the intervention cycles a hybrid process of inductive and deductive analysis was used to interpret the research data. Quantitative data from the pre and post intervention assessments was collated using Microsoft Excel. The programme was then used to create graphs to represent the data pictorially. Inductive analysis was used to investigate the study's qualitative data from focus group interviews and pupil surveys. Semi-structured focus group interviews were transcribed verbatim with codes assigned to responses that prompted common themes. These codes and similar findings from the pupil surveys were amalgamated to form categories, which were used to create themes. The deductive approach aimed to test theory and analyse data based on assertions used to design the research question at the outset. The analysis then assessed whether the collected data supported those hypotheses. Similarities between the inductively coded data were observed and triangulated with the numerical evidence from the quantitative research.

Table 1

Data Collection Method, Stage of Research and Group Researched

Data Collection	Research Stage	Research Group
<i>Drumcondra Primary Maths Test</i>	Pre and Post Intervention	Intervention, Control
<i>Measures Content Test</i>	Pre and Post Intervention	Intervention, Control
<i>Measurement Practical Test</i>	Post Intervention	Intervention, Control
<i>Focus Group Interviews</i>	Pre and Post Intervention	Intervention Group
<i>'Measurement and Me' Survey</i>	Pre and Post Intervention	Intervention Group
<i>Teacher Observation</i>	Pre and Post Intervention	Intervention Group
<i>Reflective Journaling</i>	Pre and Post Intervention	Intervention Group

Results

In pre-tests, both groups performed best on the weight strand unit and poorly on area. Post-test findings for the Drumcondra and Measures content tests revealed improvements in all three strand units for both the intervention and control groups, with the most comprehensive increment reported in area (see Figure 1). There was no reduction in the difference between both groups in mathematical knowledge and ability due to the intervention. In fact, the control group showed higher average gains in two of the strand units of length, weight and area (8.7%, 2.1%, 13.5%) compared to the intervention group (2.2%, 5.6%, 11.1%). In contrast, results from the maths trail practical assessment showed an advantage for the intervention group. Employing skills not evaluated in the pen and paper tests, the intervention group performed better in most tasks. They measured or estimated more accurately on six of the seven length tasks and four of the five area and weight tasks.

Figure 2

Post Intervention Improvements for Strand Areas (Percentage Increase)

Prior to the intervention, 14% of pupils stated they ‘don’t like Maths’ and cited a lack of stimulation and boredom as the reasons. When asked, ‘If you had a choice, what part of Maths would you get rid of?’ their responses indicated a clear distaste for strand units within ‘Number’ and an overreliance on the textbook. There was a change in pupil attitude towards maths as a result of the intervention. They reported enjoying the teaching approaches, in particular the collaborative and contextual nature of the activities. They indicated high satisfaction levels for using equipment and manipulatives (89%) and working with their hands (94%) during the intervention. Project work emerged from focus groups as a valued approach. When asked if they preferred it to book work, three quarters of the group replied that they did, citing collaboration with others and it being more ‘fun’ as the contributing factors.

In contrast, when asked if they enjoyed using the textbook, only 29% reported favourably. However, there was widespread acknowledgment that a textbook remains an important resource for teaching with the majority responding that they appreciated a mix of textbook and non-textbook work and saw the need for both with respect to activities like homework. It was observed that these sixth class pupils could discern that ‘fun’ and effective

optimal learning experiences are not always accordant. This was evident in responses to the question of whether they *learned* more from project work and which they *preferred*. As one student stated, “*I prefer doing a mix of both because for homework, you learn more than as well as-- so if you can do the hands-on projects in school maybe and then the homework off the book, then you're getting a bit of both. And so you're learning, you're getting the best of both worlds*”. There was a considerable endorsement for collaborative lessons with peers alongside the enquiry-based learning and open-ended tasks, which were both elementary focal points in the intervention. Concerning the guidance level from their teacher in such task-work, most pupils felt the teacher’s role was still important but perhaps different from what has been the case traditionally. 79% of the class pupils liked when the teacher *showed* them how to do something, but subsequent to the intervention, pupils who liked *listening to the teacher talk and explain* methods decreased from 57% to 39%. This was described by another student as “*I think a mix of both because there are some things you can’t explain but the book might explain it better*”.

Discussion and Conclusions

Analysis of quantitative and qualitative data from this research leads us to arrive at three conclusions. First, *when the method of assessment matches instruction, results for both groups improve*. The post intervention results demonstrated a difference in the performances of both groups in the written and practical evaluations. These differences can be attributed to the match between the instruction and assessment methods. The control group did best on written assessment because this form of assessment matched the nature of instruction provided through the predominant traditional textbook approach they encountered. Similarly, the intervention group performed better in the practical assessments because this was the nature of instruction that they encountered. Second, *a mix of instruction methods, both constructivist and didactic approaches, constitutes best practice in supporting a diversity of learning styles*. Neither of the two approaches, constructivist or didactic, suited all pupils. The post intervention evaluations established that many pupils from both groups recorded a decrease in their scores. The focus group interviews and surveys demonstrated that the pupils discounted no single method of learning. Furthermore, the intervention itself only marginally altered the children’s views. The pupils enjoyed the hands-on nature of constructivist maths but also had a considerable propensity for listening to instruction from their teacher. While not popular with the majority of the class, textbook exercises were still valued by many, and this opinion amplified after the intervention. Finally, *while indicating greater stimulation from engagement with constructivist approaches, pupil feedback also reveals their belief that an integration of both constructivist and didactic approaches is most beneficial for their learning*. The intervention brought about improvements in attitudes toward maths. Pupils enjoyed the collaborative and tactile nature of the lessons and ‘going outside’ the classroom to see learned skills performed in context. Although the feedback suggested pupils were unsure which method was ultimately more beneficial academically, there was an appreciation for the use of didactic approaches in certain situations, albeit a discernible preference for project-based maths over book centred tuition.

In conclusion, in a pupil-centred curriculum, there is a compelling need for educators to use a mixture of pedagogies to address and complement pupils' learning needs and preferences. Concurrent with this is the requirement that practices of assessment align with the pedagogies being used and a standardised means of evaluating hands on or practical learning be developed and implemented. As shown in the constructivist intervention of this study, practical hands-on maths has a central role in learning and has added value for pupils in terms of promoting the higher order maths skills of reasoning and problem solving. Measures, in particular, is an area of maths that allows for a transferability from what happens in the classroom to the real world. There is a need to be consistently mindful of this in the way it is taught. Although much of the strand's focus on computation is necessary, educators and policymakers need to ask what measurement applications and skills are most commonly used beyond the classroom and determine whether these are reflected in teaching methods? Ireland's STEM Policy Statement (DES, 2017) reports that learning experiences, such as those utilised in this study, support the development of dispositions that are essential in promoting STEM subjects and attracting pupils to studying STEM subjects. That continuum begins at the primary level and is influenced very much by how educators present mathematics to pupils in Irish classrooms.

References

- Cannella, G., & Reiff, J. (1994). Individual constructivist teacher education: Teachers as empowered learners. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 21(3), 27-38.
- Clerkin, A., Perkins, R., & Cunningham, R. (2016). *TIMSS 2015 in Ireland: Mathematics and science in primary and post-primary schools*. Educational Research Centre.
- Department of Education and Science (DES) (2005a). *An evaluation of curriculum implementation in primary schools*. The Stationery Office.
- Delaney, S. (2012). *A validation study of the use of mathematical knowledge for teaching measures in Ireland*. *ZDM*, 44(3), 427-441.
- Delaney, S. (2016). How to be the teacher everyone wants. News: Education, *Irish Independent*, 01.12.16, Available: <https://www.independent.ie/irish-news/education/how-to-be-the-teacher-everyone-wants-35254506.html>
- Eivers, E., & Clerkin, A. (2012) PIRLS & TIMSS 2011: *Reading, mathematics and science outcomes for Ireland*. Educational Research Centre. Available: http://www.erc.ie/documents/pt_2011_main_report.pdf. [Accessed 12 May 2019]
- Eivers, E., Shiel, G., & Cunningham, R. (2007) *Ready for tomorrow's world? The competencies of Irish 15-year-olds in PISA 2006 summary report*. Available online at: http://www.erc.ie/documents/tomorrows_world.pdf
- Fosnot, C.T. (2005). Constructivism revisited: Implications and reflections. *The Constructivist*, 16(1).

- Glaserfeld, E. (1996). Introduction: Aspects of constructivism. In C. T. Fosnot (Ed.), *Constructivism: Theory, perspectives and practice* (pp. 3-7). Teachers College Press.
- Johnson, P., O'Meara, N. & Leavy, A.M. (2020). Factors supporting and inhibiting teachers' use of manipulatives around the primary to post-primary education transition. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 1-23.
- Larochelle, M., Bednarz, N., & Garrison, J. (Eds.) (1998). *Constructivism and education*. Cambridge Press.
- O'Meara, N., Johnson, P. & Leavy, A. M. (2019). A comparative study investigating the use of manipulatives at the transition from primary to post-primary education. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 51(6), 835-857. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2019.1634842>
- National Council for Curriculum Assessment (1999). *Primary mathematics curriculum teacher guidelines*. NCCA.
- National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (2016). *Background paper and brief for the development of a new primary maths curriculum*. NCCA
- Noddings, N., (1985). Small groups as a setting for research on mathematical problem solving. In E. A. Silver (ed.), *Teaching and learning mathematical problem solving: Multiple research perspectives*. LEA.
- Perkins, R., & Clerkin, A. (2020). *TIMSS 2019: Ireland's results in mathematics and science*. Educational Research Centre.
- Shiel, G., Kavanagh, L., & Millar, D. (2014). *The 2014 national assessments of English reading and mathematics Volume 1: Performance report*. ERC Centre.
- Surgenor, P., G. Shiel, S. Close and D. Millar, (2006) *Counting on success: Mathematics achievement in Irish primary schools*. Department of Education and Science Inspectorate.